

Accessibility of Electronic Banking Services and Facilities Among Persons with Disabilities in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

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Abstract

This descriptive study examined access to electronic banking among 100 students with disabilities at the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, using a validated questionnaire ($\alpha = 0.78$). Respondents included students with hearing (56%), physical (24%), visual (10%), and health impairments (10%). Results showed that ATMs were the most used e-banking facility (71%), followed by internet banking (16%) and POS (13%). Overall satisfaction because e-banking was rated incompatible with users' needs (Mean = 2.28), lifestyles (Mean = 2.35), and inclusion (Mean = 2.44), although ease of use was rated positively (Mean = 2.83). Convenience findings were mixed: e-banking offered comfort (Mean = 2.52) and online/offline availability (Mean = 2.67), but disagreed on inclusivity and accessibility of locations (Mean = 2.44–2.48). Features related to disability-friendliness, training, and usability were poorly rated (Mean = 2.12–2.39). While some accessibility was acknowledged, such as transacting anywhere (Mean = 2.63) and resolving issues (Mean = 2.89), reliance on physical bank branches remained (Mean = 2.49). The study concluded that e-banking is only partially accessible and recommended disability-friendly features like braille interfaces, voice-to-text applications, and targeted user training.

Keywords: Electronic banking; accessibility; persons with disabilities; inclusion; Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

With advancements in Information and Communication Technologies and their ever-increasing permeation of every sphere of our lives, comes colossal growth in the volume of information and communication facilities. This has engendered qualitative and quantitative leap in the development of the global society at large and Nigeria in particular. This digital

revolution continues to evolve and the digital economy is being created. These developments have become highly pronounced on the banking systems such that Electronic banking (e-banking) products and services are of prime significance for banks that want to remain relevant in this global information and communication revolution. The modern day banking now rely greatly on e-banking which utilization depends on use of new technology to give different banking services without obstruction to clients all day and all night. Banks offer a wide range of e-banking services and products as CBN (2003) reports that the following are accessible in the Nigerian banking framework: ATM, smart cards, phone banking, personal computer (PC) banking, and web banking.

Abdullahi, Muhammad, Salisu and Usman (2018) state that the development of electronic banking rely on several variables, for example, achievement of web access, new online banking features, family unit development of web use, legitimate and administrative system for it to offer speedier, faster and reliable services to the clients for which they might be generally fulfilled than that of manual system of banking. As good as these recent developments of e-banking systems are, it have caused major changes in the way services are delivered to the customers (including customers with disabilities). Customers now use more of self-service options, which are more convenient and fast but portend several challenges for persons with disabilities. According to the World report on disability (2011), there is a reported 25 million persons living with disabilities in Nigeria, which is a considerable customer size for any bank. Consequently, in the face of increasing competition from emerging digital banks, which are redefining customer satisfaction and luring more customers, every bank must adopt a disability-friendly approach that will leverage on accessible digital channels to create a more rewarding customer satisfaction for all customers irrespective of disabilities or not.

Accessibility refers to the extent to which a product, device, service, or environment is available and navigable for persons with disabilities, or for persons with other special needs or functional limitations. Similarly, digital accessibility can level the playing field for persons with disability and allow for productivity and inclusion through participation in educational, economic, and political spheres. However, it is important to view such accessibility as beneficial for everyone, and not just one sub-group, though accessibility may have originated to facilitate matters for a particular sub-group (Kulkarni 2018). According to the Global Initiative for Inclusive Information and Communication Technologies (G3ict, 2015a), the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) was adopted by the United Nations on December 13, 2006. It has since been signed by 159 countries and ratified by 151 countries as of December 2014. Additionally, 92 countries have signed the Optional Protocol to the Convention and 85 have ratified it. The Convention has championed the rights of persons with disabilities and the importance of improving their accessibility to services: The Convention follows decades of work by the United Nations to change attitudes and approaches to persons with disabilities. It takes to a new height the movement from viewing persons with disabilities as “objects” of charity, medical treatment and social protection towards viewing persons with disabilities as “subjects” with rights, who are capable of claiming those rights and making decisions for their lives based on their free and informed consent as well as being active members of society. For instance Article 9 of the UNCRPD states:

To enable persons with disabilities to live independently and participate fully in all aspects of life, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications, including information and communications technologies

and systems, and to other facilities and services open or provided to the public, both in urban and in rural areas. These measures, which shall include the identification and elimination of obstacles and barriers to accessibility, shall apply to, inter alia:

- a. Buildings, roads, transportation and other indoor and outdoor facilities, including schools, housing, medical facilities and workplaces;*
- b. Information, communications and other services, including electronic services and emergency services.*

As observed by G3ict (2015b), the biggest obstacle that comes with developing e-banking options which are accessible to all is the wide diversity in the persons who are trying to access the banks' websites with or without assistive technologies or aids. It therefore recommended a universal design. The goal of universal design is to have each web page accessible by all persons, instead of providing separate web pages for persons with disabilities. This requires, for example, for persons who are blind, adjustable fonts or contrasts, keyboard navigation, textual equivalents for all images, and reading order and structure compatible with screen reading or text augmentation tools or devices and magnifiers; for persons who are deaf, visual equivalents such as captions for all audio information; and for persons with motor disabilities, means to navigate the page without fine motor control.

Despite plausible efforts in terms of policies and initiatives such as by UNCRPD and G3ict to improve overall accessibility of persons with disabilities in all spheres of life and most the banking sector not much has been achieved in Nigeria in this regard. Inclusion of persons with disabilities and their consequent financial inclusion are not only fundamental human rights but a necessity for a holistic growth of the banking system and national economy. However, judging by what obtains in Nigeria majority of the banking services and products are not yet accessible for persons with disabilities. For example, most of the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) points are physically inaccessible for persons with physical and health impairments let alone that they will go near it to withdraw cash. Equally, the keyboards on the ATMs and Point of Sales (POS) machines used by vendors are not brailled. Whereas persons with hearing impairment can see and can navigate bank facilities easy they do not have adequate knowledge of how to use the e-banking services and product due to absence of sign language compliant facilities. All these have contributed to the inability of persons with disabilities to take advantage of these facilities.

This research work therefore came at the right time to determine the extent of accessibility persons with disabilities have by using the e-banking facilities available to them in Nigerian banks.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to survey the accessibility of electronic banking services and facilities among persons with disabilities in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Specific purposes will include:

- To determine how well e-banking services and products meet the needs of persons with disabilities
- To determine how convenient e-banking services and products are for persons with disabilities
- To determine how well features of the e- banking meet the peculiar needs of persons with disabilities

- To determine how accessible of e-banking services and products are for persons with disabilities

Research questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

- To what degree do e-banking services and products meet the needs of persons with disabilities?
- How convenient are the e-banking services and products for persons with disabilities
- To what extent do the features of the e- banking meet the peculiar needs of persons with disabilities
- What is the degree of accessibility of e-banking services and products by persons with disabilities

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive research design. By its nature the research was a fact-finding attempt to describe, record, analyse and interpret conditions of accessibility of e banking service as they existed among persons with disabilities. The population for this study consisted of all students with disabilities of FCE (Special), Oyo, the only higher institution of learning for persons with disabilities in Sub-Sahara Africa. 100 students were randomly selected for the purpose this study. The students were served the questionnaire and were guided to fill it appropriately. A self-structured questionnaire for this study was named Disability, Accessibility and Electronic Banking Questionnaire (DAEBQ).

The validity and reliability of the test were ascertained by professionals in the field of test and measurement by pilot test. Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to analyse the results in order to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument. Reliability and validity of 0.78 and 0.80 respectively were achieved by items of the instrument. The results were analysed using the descriptive statistics which entailed frequency count, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Table 1: Gender of participants

Item	Frequency	Percent
Male	37	37.0
Female	63	63.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1 reveals that out of the 100 participants, **37% were male** and **63% were female**, showing that the majority of respondents were women.

Table 2: Age of participants

	Frequency	Percent
15-19	52	52.0
20-24	44	44.0
25 above	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 reveals most respondents were young, with **52% aged 15–19 years**, **44% aged 20–24 years**, and only **4% above 25 years**. This indicates that the study sample was largely made up of youth.

Table 3: Educational level of Participants

	Frequency	Percent
100	31	31.0
200	34	34.0
300	35	35.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 reveals participants were fairly evenly distributed across academic levels, with **31% in 100 level**, **34% in 200 level**, and **35% in 300 level**, showing balanced representation from different stages of tertiary education.

Table 4 Types of E-banking

Facility	Frequency	Percent
ATM	71	71.0
POS	13	13.0
INTERNET BANKING	16	16.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 shows that the most commonly used e-banking facility was the **ATM (71%)**, followed by **Internet Banking (16%)**, and **POS (13%)**. This suggests that ATMs are the primary channel of e-banking access among persons with disabilities.

Table 5: Nature of Disability of Participants

	Frequency	Percent
Hearing Impairment	56	56.0
Visual Impairment	10	10.0
Physical Impairment	24	24.0
Health Impairment	10	10.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 shows that highest proportion of participants had **hearing impairment (56%)**, followed by **physical impairment (24%)**, while **visual impairment (10%)** and **health impairment (10%)** were less represented.

Research Question 1: To what degree do e-banking services and products meet the needs of persons with disabilities?

The decision rule for the question items is: **1.00 – 1.49 → Strongly Disagree**
1.50 – 2.49 → Disagree
2.50 – 3.49 → Agree
3.50 – 4.00 → Strongly Agree

Table 6: Summary of the Degree to which e-Banking Services and Products Meet the Needs of Persons with Disabilities

Question item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Compatible with my needs	2.28	1.045	Disagree
Easy to use despite disability	2.83	2.193	Agree
Compatible with my life styles	2.35	1.067	Disagree
It is a sign of inclusion	2.44	1.085	Disagree
My friends tell me it is disability-friendly	2.28	.965	Disagree

Table 6 shows that most items fall within the “**Disagree**” range (1.50 – 2.49). Specifically, participants **disagreed** that e-banking services are compatible with their needs (Mean=2.28), lifestyles (Mean=2.35), or that they represent inclusion (Mean=2.44). They also **disagreed** with the idea that friends consider e-banking disability-friendly (Mean=2.28). The only positively rated item was “**Easy to use despite disability**” (M=2.83), which falls in the “**Agree**” range (2.50 – 3.49), indicating that, despite limitations, participants find e-banking somewhat usable.

Research Question 2: How convenient are the e-banking services and products for persons with disabilities

Table 7: Summary of the Convenience of E-banking Services and Products for Persons with Disabilities

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Has disability-friendly facilities	2.43	1.057	Disagree
Brings general comfort	2.52	1.000	Agree
Location is accessible	2.48	.969	Disagree
Are found at prominent locations	2.44	1.057	Disagree
Offline and online available	2.67	1.025	Agree

Table 7 indicates a mixed experience of convenience. Participants generally **disagreed** that e-banking services have disability-friendly facilities (Mean=2.43), are easily accessible in terms of location (Mean=2.48), or are found at prominent locations (Mean=2.44). However, they **agreed** that e-banking services **bring general comfort** (Mean=2.52) and are available **both offline and online** (Mean=2.67).

Research Question 3: To what extent do the features of the e- banking meet the peculiar needs of persons with disabilities?

Table 8: Summary of the Extent to Which Features of E- Banking Meet the Peculiar Needs of Persons with Disabilities

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Disability friendly	2.34	1.085	Disagree
Has e-banking training	2.39	.973	Disagree
I know how to use it	2.12	1.148	Disagree
Bank offers e-banking training	2.24	1.093	Disagree
Adequately explained procedures	2.35	1.077	Disagree

Table 8 reveals all the items fall within the “Disagree” range (1.50–2.49). Participants generally **disagreed** that e-banking is disability friendly (Mean=2.34), provides adequate training (Mean=2.39), or that banks offer such training (Mean=2.24). They also **disagreed** that they know how to use e-banking (Mean=2.12) and that procedures are adequately explained (Mean=2.35).

Research question 4: What is the degree of accessibility of e-banking services and products by persons with disabilities?

Table 9: Summary of the Degree of Accessibility of E-Banking Services and Products By Persons with Disabilities

Accessibility of e-banking	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
I can bank anywhere	2.63	.981	Agree
Easily transact	2.58	1.093	Agree
Easily interact with bank	2.54	.979	Agree
I hardly visit bank	2.49	1.049	Disagree
Can easily resolve banking issues	2.89	3.210	Agree

Table 9 reveals most items fall within the “Agree” range (2.50–3.49). Participants agreed that they can bank anywhere (Mean=2.63), easily transact (Mean=2.58), easily interact with the bank (Mean=2.54), and can resolve banking issues (Mean=2.89). However, they disagreed with the statement “I hardly visit the bank” (Mean=2.49), suggesting that despite accessibility through e-banking, many still need to physically visit bank branches.

Discussion of Findings

The sample for this study predominantly comprises young female students—63% female, with 52% aged 15–19 and another 44% aged 20–24, and educational levels evenly distributed (100, 200, 300 levels). The majority of participants have hearing impairments (56%), followed by physical (24%) and visual/health impairments (10% each). This demographic skew indicates that the voices represented come from relatively young, educated persons with disabilities—yet their views may not reflect older or less educated individuals. Significantly, the high representation of participants with hearing impairment may mean accessibility needs specific to visual impairment, such as screen-reader compatibility or audio-enabled interfaces, are underrepresented in the responses. As a result, the findings likely reflect certain accessibility challenges more than others.

Also, findings consistently reveal dissatisfaction with e-banking services in terms of compatibility, accessibility, disability-friendliness, and training. Out of the 15 items across these tables, 14 fall in the “Disagree” range (means between 1.50–2.49), while only one item—“Easy to use despite disability”, receives a weak “Agree” (2.83). This aligns with studies in Nigeria revealing systemic accessibility failures: many bank apps and websites remain incompatible with assistive tools like screen readers, contain unlabelled buttons, lack alt text or voice features, and user experience varies widely even within the same bank’s platforms. These usability shortcomings foster exclusion and hinder independence, confirming your sample’s strong negative perception of platform features and support mechanisms (Puli et al., 2024)

While comfort and dual access (online/offline) received marginal agreement, more explicit indicators of convenience and accessibility, such as disability-friendly facilities and reduced physical visits, stayed in the “Disagree” range. Participants generally agreed that e-banking enables them to bank anywhere (2.63), transact easily (2.58), interact with banks (2.54), and resolve issues (2.89). Yet, they disagreed with the claim “I hardly visit the bank” (2.49), implying ongoing reliance on physical branches despite digital access. This mirrors findings from **Ofuani-Sokolo & Monye’s (2024)** report on PWDs in Nigeria, where inaccessible physical infrastructure, unhelpful staff, and poorly designed digital systems continue to force physical visits and assistance. So, while e-banking offers functional convenience in principle, pervasive design and structural barriers undermine full independence and continuous digital adoption.

Implication of the Study

The implications of this study are obvious in the fact that although e-banking services and products are generally accessible, they still need further improvement to ensure that their features are made disability-friendly and disability friendly so that the specific banking needs of persons with disabilities are catered for.

Conclusion

Although e-banking services and products remain fairly accessible to persons with disabilities, there are still specific areas of it that requires improvement in order to make the products and services more accessible

Recommendations

These recommendations are made considering the findings of this study:

- A. The features of e-banking should encompass disability friendly features such as brailed interface and voice-to-text applications
- B. Persons with disabilities should be well-trained by banks regarding how to effectively use their e-banking services and products.
- C. Banks’ members of staff should be well trained on how to meet the peculiar needs of customers with disabilities.
- D. POS and ATM machines should be designed with disability disability-friendly facilities
- E. Persons with disabilities should hesitate to educate banks concerning areas of e- banking services and products that need to be improved.

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